

Supplementary Text for Grabowski, M (in press). *Blouch*: Bayesian Linear Ornstein-Uhlenbeck models for Comparative Hypotheses. Systematic Biology.

1. Multi-Optima Model: Following Hansen (1997), *Blouch* models the evolution of a response variable as an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process toward a primary optimal state that is a function of categorical predictor variables (e.g. social systems) mapped as regimes on the phylogeny, a relationship expressed as the stochastic differential equation:

$$dY = -\alpha(Y - \theta(T))dt + \sigma_Y dB_{yY}$$

where dY is changes in the response variable, Y , over a small time interval, dt , α is the rate of adaptation of Y towards the optimum θ , modeled as a function of the categorical predictors mapped on the phylogeny, T , and can be expressed as the phylogenetic half-life, $t_{1/2} = \ln(2) / \alpha$, dB is a white-noise process (independent normally distributed random changes with mean 0 and unit variance) and σ is the standard deviation of the random changes, which can be expressed as the stationary variance, $v = \sigma_Y^2 / 2\alpha$, the equilibrium variance of an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process evolving around a stationary optimum, θ .

2. Adaptive Model: *Blouch* implements the model of adaptive evolution introduced by Hansen et al. (2008). Here the response variable evolves according to an Ornstein-Uhlenbeck process towards an optimal state that is modeled as a function of the predictor variable, a relationship expressed as the stochastic differential equations:

$$\begin{aligned} dY &= -\alpha(Y - \theta(x))dt + \sigma_Y dB_Y \\ dX &= \sigma_X dB_X \end{aligned}$$

where dY is changes in the response variable, Y , over a small time interval, dt , α is the rate of adaptation of Y towards the optimum θ and can be expressed as the phylogenetic half-life, $t_{1/2}$, dB is a white-noise process and σ is the standard deviation of the random changes for the X and Y variables. The relationship of the optimum to the predictor variable is the linear regression $\theta = b_0 + b_1X$ (Hansen et al. 2008). The predictor is assumed to evolve as if by a Brownian-motion process.

The adaptation model estimates the optimal and evolutionary regressions, the former the relationship between the response and predictor that would be achieved if the response was able to adapt fast enough to perfectly track changes in the predictor; the latter is the generalized least square regression of the response on the predictor and is influenced by both adaptation and inertia (see Hansen et al. 2008 for complete derivations).

3. Direct Effect Model: *Blouch* also implements the model of constrained evolution (Hansen and Bartoszek 2012) previously implemented in Grabowski et al. (2016, see also 2023), which can be used to test for allometric constraints. Here, changes in the predictor (dX) are associated with an immediate correlated response in the response variable:

$$\begin{aligned} dY &= -\alpha(Y - \theta)dt + b dX + \sigma_Y dB_Y \\ dX &= \sigma_X dB_X \end{aligned}$$

Notation is as above with the addition of b , a slope parameter that directly scales the change in X with the change in Y . In the direct effect model, θ is the intercept of the optimal relationship between the two traits, α describes the rate of adaptation towards the optima, while the relationship between Y and X solely due to the b term.

4. Phylogenetic Correlations: Residual error for all models may be due to genetic correlations with other traits, environmental changes, and evolutionary forces such as genetic drift and mutation. This error may have phylogenetic structure due to other unmeasured traits that influence Y , and these phylogenetic correlations are the justification for using phylogenetic comparative methods. (Grafen 1989; Hansen 1997; Uyeda et al. 2018). While Brownian motion is often assumed when modeling the pattern of phylogenetic correlations in the model residuals, here the degree of phylogenetic correlation in the residuals is estimated from the data and measured by the phylogenetic half-life ($t_{1/2}$). For the multi-optima and adaptive models, a short half-life (a small percentage of the length of the phylogeny) means little phylogenetic inertia and the response variable is adapting rapidly towards θ , leading to convergence between the optimal and evolutionary regressions. A long half-life life (i.e. \sim multiple times the length of the phylogeny) means that the response trait is evolving slowly but can have trends influenced by the predictors. For the direct effect model, half-life merely shows the phylogenetic

inertia of the model residuals and given a long half-life the model converges on Brownian motion. If evolution is strictly constrained by allometry, the direct effect slope should equal the slope of static or ontogenetic allometry (Hansen and Bartoszek 2012; Grabowski et al. 2016). See Hansen et al. (2008), Hansen and Bartoszek (2012) and Grabowski et al. (2016) for complete details.

5. Pareto-Smoothed Importance Sampling for Cross-validation (PSIS): Models can learn too much from an individual sample that is not generalizable to other samples, known as overfitting, or too little, known as underfitting (McElreath 2020). Models that are overfit, for example by using many parameters, will tend to fit the training sample extremely well, but fit out-of-sample observations poorly – thus they are not generalizable outside the training sample. Models that are underfit will tend to fit both sets of observations poorly. While underfitting is relatively easy to assess, overfitting is much more difficult and can often be ignored (Silver 2012). A model’s predictive performance (the ability to predict future observations) provides a way to assess its degree of overfitting. Cross-validation (Stone 1974) and Information Criteria (Akaike 1974) are two general approaches for assessing predictive performance, and have been recently applied to Bayesian Phylogenetics (Lartillot 2023). I focus on Bayesian cross-validation here but note that because *Blouch* calculates the pointwise log-likelihood values and returns them in the posterior, making Information Criteria approaches such as Widely Applicable Information Criterion (WAIC) available (Watanabe 2010). In cross-validation, including leave-one-out cross-validation, a model is trained on one part of the dataset, and then its ability at predicting observations in the other part is assessed. Exact Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation requires calculating the posterior distribution for each observation, which can be extremely time-consuming depending on the complexity of the model and the size of the dataset (Vehtari et al. 2017). Pareto-Smoothed Importance Sampling is one approach for approximating Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation using a single posterior distribution, providing an estimate of the expected log pointwise predictive density (elpd) (Vehtari et al. 2017). Importantly, Pareto-Smoothed Importance Sampling also includes a metric for assessing the reliability of the approximation in the form of Pareto shape parameter k diagnostics. As Pareto k diagnostics are point-wise – they show which observations in the dataset are particularly hard to estimate, with diagnostics > 0.7 suggesting that the estimates are not reliable (Vehtari et al. 2017). Thus, in addition to overall reliability of the estimate, Pareto k diagnostics can potentially reveal outliers for inspection (McElreath 2020; Vehtari et al. 2022).

6. Bayes Factors: Bayes Factors are the ratio of the marginal likelihoods – the probability of the observed data given the model – for two models, and can be used as an estimate of predictive performance, penalizing for model complexity (Vehtari and Ojanen 2012). Bayes Factors are notoriously difficult to estimate given complex models, though several Monte Carlo sampling methods have been suggested (Gronau et al. 2017) including bridge sampling. Bridge sampling has been shown to perform accurately given complex and hierarchical models (Meng and Wong 1996; Meng and Schilling 2002) and here Bayesian model comparison using Bayes Factors is calculated in the R Package *bridgesampling* (Gronau et al. 2020). In bridge sampling, a proposal distribution and a bridge function are chosen – the former is a multivariate normal distribution with a mean vector and covariance matrix that mirror the posterior sample quantities, which has been shown to work across a range of situations (Gronau et al. 2017), while the latter in the *bridgesampling* package is a function that minimizes the relative mean square error of the estimator (Meng and Wong 1996). The package then estimates the marginal likelihood iterating from an initial guess of the marginal likelihood until convergence (see Gronau et al. 2017, 2020).

New Implementations

Multilevel Multi-Optima and Varying Effects Models: For the multi-optima models or models that are a combination of categorical regimes and continuous predictors, *Blouch* can fit multilevel models that allow information to be shared across regimes, allowing for both varying intercepts or optima and varying slopes with partial pooling between parameters (Gelman et al. 2013; McElreath 2020). Partial pooling allows balancing of overfitting – where models learn too much from the data – and underfitting – where models learn too little from the data. Priors for all hyperparameters below are based on their use in model validation but should be changed based on prior predictive simulation. *Blouch* can also fit non-multilevel varying effects models as shown below, where intercepts and slopes can vary but there is no partial pooling.

7. Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model with Varying Effects

This model includes varying intercepts across the regimes but also varying slopes for the direct effect predictor, X . This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed in the main text. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\ Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
u_i &= dmX_i\theta_{reg[i]} + X_{True,i}\beta_{reg[i]} \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\beta_{reg[i]} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

where $Y_{Obs,i}$ is the observed species values with a normal distribution centered on the true species values, $Y_{True,i}$ with estimated standard error $Y_{SE,i}$, $Y_{True,i}$ is the true species values with a multivariate Gaussian distribution with mean u_i and variance/covariance matrix V , u_i is defined as the sum of the product of dmX_i and $\theta_{reg[i]}$, and $X_{True,i}$ and $\beta_{reg[i]}$, with dmX a design matrix with number of rows equal to the number of species and number of columns equal to the number of regimes θ and elements giving the sum of weights of segments on the tree T where the optima was $\theta_{reg[i]}$ and is a function of the phylogenetic half-life, $t_{1/2}$, and the phylogeny, T , following Hansen (1997), $\theta_{reg[i]}$ is a vector with each element the optimal value for a given regime, $X_{True,i}$ is the true species value for the X variables and is estimated in the same manner as $Y_{True,i}$, $\beta_{reg[i]}$ is the direct effect model slope and varies per regime, and V is defined as in Hansen (1997) as is a function of $t_{1/2}$, the stationary variance, v , and T , the phylogeny.

8. Multi-Optima Adaptive Model with Varying Effects

This model includes varying intercepts across the regimes and varying slopes for the adaptive predictor, X . This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables by treating the true quantities as missing data to be estimated (Clayton 1992; Richardson and Gilks 1993).

The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i\theta_{reg[i]} + [X_{True,i}\rho]\beta_{reg[i]} \\
\rho &= h(t_{1/2}, T) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\beta_{reg[i]} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,0.25) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, \beta, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

where notation is as above but the term before $\beta_{reg[i]}$ in the definition of u_i is now the product of the matrix of with columns equal to the adaptive predictor and ρ , the phylogenetic correction factor, with ρ a function of $t_{1/2}$ and T (Hansen et al. 2008).

9. Multilevel Multi-Optima Model with Varying Intercepts

This model includes varying intercepts model across regimes but uses a multilevel approach to allow for partial pooling. This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i\theta_{reg[i]}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \text{Normal}(\bar{\theta}, \sigma) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 1) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(5) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20)
\end{aligned}$$

Where notation is as above but $\theta_{reg[i]}$ is a vector with each element the optimal value for a given regime and has a normal distribution centered on $\bar{\theta}$ with standard deviation σ .

10. Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model with Varying Intercepts

As in the previous model, this model includes varying intercepts across the regimes, but also includes a direct effect predictor, X . This model allows for partial pooling across intercepts. This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]} + X_{True,i} \beta \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \text{Normal}(\bar{\theta}, \sigma) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 1) \\
\beta &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.25) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(5) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)
\end{aligned}$$

Notation is the same as defined above, with u_i now being determined by the sum of $dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]}$ and the product of $X_{True,i}$ and a single direct effect slope, β .

11. Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptive Model with Varying Intercepts

As in the previous model we use varying intercepts model for the optima, but here includes an adaptive predictor, X . This model allows for partial pooling across intercepts. This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]} + [X_{True,i} \rho] \beta \\
\rho &= h(t_{1/2}, T) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \text{Normal}(\bar{\theta}, \sigma) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 1) \\
\beta &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 0.25) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(5) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)
\end{aligned}$$

where u_i now being determined by the sum of $dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]}$ and the product of $X_{True,i}$, the phylogenetic correction factor ρ , and the optimal slope, β , with ρ a function of $t_{1/2}$ and T (Hansen et al. 2008).

12. Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect and Adaptive Model with Varying Intercepts

As in the previous model we use varying intercepts model for the optima, but here includes both direct effect and adaptive predictors. This model allows for partial pooling across intercepts. This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]} + [X_{d,True,i}, (X_{a,True,i} \rho)] \beta \\
\rho &= h(t_{1/2}, T) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \text{Normal}(\bar{\theta}, \sigma) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\beta &\sim \text{Normal}(0,0.25) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(5) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

Notation is as above but the term before β in the definition of u_i is now a matrix with columns equal to the direct effect predictors, $X_{d,True}$, and columns equal to the product of the adaptive predictors, $X_{a,True}$, and ρ .

13. Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model with Varying Effects

This model includes varying intercepts across the regimes but also varying slopes for the direct effect predictor, X , and includes a joint population of varying intercepts and slopes. This approach allows for partial pooling across intercepts and slopes. This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]} + X_{True,i} \beta_{reg[i]} \\
[\theta_{reg[i]}, \beta_{reg[i]}] &\sim \text{MVNormal}([\bar{\theta}, \bar{\beta}], R, [\sigma_\theta, \sigma_\beta]) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\bar{\beta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,0.25) \\
\sigma_\theta &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
\sigma_\beta &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
Rho &\sim \text{LJKCorr}(4) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

All notation is the same as defined above but $\theta_{reg[i]}$ and $\beta_{reg[i]}$ now have a joint multivariate Gaussian distribution centered on $\bar{\theta}$ and $\bar{\beta}$ with correlation matrix R and standard deviation for the optima of σ_θ and for the slopes σ_β . The prior for Rho is the Lewandowski-Kurowicka-Joe distribution.

14. Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptive Model with Varying Effects

This model includes varying intercepts across the regimes and varying slopes for the adaptive predictor, X , and includes a joint population of varying intercepts and slopes. This approach allows partial pooling across the parameters. This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$Y_{Obs,i} \sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]} + [X_{True,i} \rho] \beta_{reg[i]} \\
\rho &= h(t_{1/2}, T) \\
[\theta_{reg[i]}, \beta_{reg[i]}] &\sim \text{MVNormal}([\bar{\theta}, \bar{\beta}], R, [\sigma_\theta, \sigma_\beta]) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\bar{\beta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,0.25) \\
\sigma_\theta &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
\sigma_\beta &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
Rho &\sim \text{LJKCorr}(4) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, \beta, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

where notation is as above but the term before $\beta_{reg[i]}$ in the definition of u_i is now a matrix with columns equal to the product of the adaptive predictors, $X_{a,True}$, and ρ .

15. Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect and Adaptive Model with Varying Effects

This model includes varying intercepts across the regimes and varying slopes for the direct effect X_d and adaptive predictor, X_a , and includes a joint population of varying intercepts and slopes. This approach allows partial pooling across the parameters. This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]} + [X_{d,True,i}(X_{a,True,i} \rho)] \beta_{reg[i]} \\
\rho &= h(t_{1/2}, T) \\
[\theta_{reg[i]}, \beta_{reg[i]}] &\sim \text{MVNormal}([\bar{\theta}, \bar{\beta}], R, [\sigma_\theta, \sigma_\beta]) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\bar{\beta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,0.25) \\
\sigma_\theta &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
\sigma_\beta &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
Rho &\sim \text{LJKCorr}(4) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, \beta, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

where notation is as above but the term before $\beta_{reg[i]}$ in the definition of u_i is now a matrix with columns equal to the direct effect predictors, $X_{d,True}$, and the product of the adaptive predictors, $X_{a,True}$, and ρ .

Non-centered Multilevel Models: *Blouch* also has non-centered versions of the multilevel models introduced above. This reparameterization can reduce divergent transitions – regions of the posterior distribution that are difficult to explore (Stan Development Team 2023), by moving the parameters embedded in stochastic definitions of other parameters out and changing their relationship to deterministic (see below for examples)(McElreath 2020; Stan Development Team 2023). Priors for non-hyperparameters below are based on their use in model validation but should be changed based on prior predictive simulation.

16. Multilevel Multi-Optima Model with Varying Intercepts – Non-centered

Blouch employs a varying intercepts model for regimes, reparametrizing the statistical model as a non-centered version to move hyperparameters ($\bar{\theta}$) out of the definition of θ . Here z is the standardized θ , calculated by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation, with mean 0 and standard deviation 1. This model includes measurement error in the Y variable, following the approach discussed above. Following Hansen (1997), the full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]} \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\theta} + Z\sigma \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
Z &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(5) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20)
\end{aligned}$$

where $Y_{Obs,i}$ is the observed species values with a normal distribution centered on the true species values, $Y_{True,i}$ with known standard error $Y_{SE,i}$, $Y_{True,i}$ is the true species values with a multivariate Gaussian distribution with mean u and variance/covariance matrix V , u is defined as the product of dmX and the optima, with dmX a design matrix with number of rows equal to the number of species and number of columns equal to the number of θ and elements giving the sum of weights of segments on the tree T where the optima was $\theta_{reg[i]}$ and is a function of the phylogenetic half-life, $t_{1/2}$, and the phylogeny, T , following Hansen (1997), θ is a vector with each element the optimal value for a given regime and is the sum of $\bar{\theta}$ and the product of z and σ , with Z a vector of z -scores and σ the standard deviation of the intercepts. V is defined as in Hansen (1997) as a function of $t_{1/2}$, the stationary variance, v , and T , the phylogeny.

17. Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model with Varying Intercepts – Non-centered

As in the previous model we use a non-centered parameterization for the optima, but here includes a direct effect predictor, X . This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= [dmX_i, X_{True,i}][\theta_{reg[i]}, \beta] \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\theta} + Z\sigma \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\beta &\sim \text{Normal}(0,0.25) \\
Z &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(5) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

with notation as above with the addition of the first term in the definition of u_i is now a matrix with columns equal to the design matrix dmX and $X_{True,i}$ and the second term is now a matrix with columns equal to $\theta_{reg[i]}$ and β .

18. Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptive Model with Varying Intercepts – Non-centered

As in the previous model we use a non-centered parameterization for the optima, but here includes an adaptive predictor, X . This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. All other notation is the same as defined above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= [dmX_i, (X_{True,i}\rho)] [\theta_{reg[i]}, \beta] \\
\rho &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\theta} + Z\sigma \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\beta &\sim \text{Normal}(0,0.25) \\
Z &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(5) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

with notation as above with the addition of the first term in the definition of u_i is now a matrix with columns equal to the design matrix dmX and the product of $X_{True,i}$ and ρ .

19. Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect Model with Varying Effects – Non-centered

This model includes varying intercepts across the regimes but also varying slopes for the direct effect predictor, X , and includes a joint population of varying intercepts and slopes. This approach allows partial pooling across the parameters. This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i\theta_{reg[i]} + X_{True,i}\beta_{reg[i]} \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\theta} + v_{,1} \\
\beta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\beta} + v_{,2} \\
v &= (\text{diag}(\sigma)LZ) \\
Z &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\bar{\beta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,0.25) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
L &\sim \text{LJKCorrCholesky}(4) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

with notation the same as above but with $\theta_{reg[i]}$ is a vector now equal to the sum of $\bar{\theta}$ and the first column of the matrix v , and $\beta_{reg[i]}$ now equal to the sum of $\bar{\beta}$ and the second column of v , with v a matrix equal to the product of the diagonal matrix σ and Cholesky correlation factor L and the matrix of z-scores, Z . Here σ is a vector of the standard deviations of $\theta_{reg[i]}$ and $\beta_{reg[i]}$. The prior for L is the Lewandowski-Kuwowicka-Joe Cholesky factor of the correlation matrix.

20. Multilevel Multi-Optima Adaptive Model with Varying Effects – Non-centered

This model includes varying intercepts across the regimes and varying slopes for the adaptive predictor, X , and includes a joint population of varying intercepts and slopes. This approach allows partial pooling across the parameters. This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i\theta + [X_{True,i}\rho]\beta_{reg[i]} \\
\rho &= h(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\theta} + v_{,1} \\
\beta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\beta} + v_{,2} \\
v &= (\text{diag}(\sigma)LZ) \\
Z &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\bar{\beta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,0.25) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
L &\sim \text{LJKCorrCholesky}(4) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, \beta, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

where notation is the same as above.

21. Multilevel Multi-Optima Direct Effect and Adaptative Model with Varying Effects – Non-centered

This model includes varying intercepts across the regimes and varying slopes for the direct predictor, X_d , and adaptative predictor, X_a , and includes a joint population of varying intercepts and slopes. This approach allows partial pooling across the parameters. This model includes measurement error in both the Y and X variables, following the approach discussed above. The full model is:

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i\theta_{reg[i]} + [X_{d,True,i}(X_{a,True,i}\rho)]\beta_{reg[i]} \\
\rho &= h(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\theta} + v_{,1} \\
\beta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\beta} + v_{,2} \\
v &= (\text{diag}(\sigma)LZ) \\
Z &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1) \\
\bar{\beta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,0.25) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
L &\sim \text{LJKCorrCholesky}(4) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, \beta, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0,1)
\end{aligned}$$

where notation is the same as above.

22. Simulation Example Model and Priors

Here we start with the multilevel multi-optima adaptative model with varying effects. Priors were set as discussed in the main text including $\bar{\theta}$ and $\bar{\beta}$ centered on the intercept and slope estimates from an ordinary least squares regression and scale parameter based on prior predictive simulation. Priors for parameters not discussed in the main text were set based on prior predictive simulation and observing the posterior.

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]} + [X_{True,i} \rho] \beta_{reg[i]} \\
\rho &= h(t_{1/2}, T) \\
[\theta_{reg[i]}, \beta_{reg[i]}] &\sim \text{MVNormal}([\bar{\theta}, \bar{\beta}], R, [\sigma_\theta, \sigma_\beta]) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(2.8, 1.0) \\
\bar{\beta} &\sim \text{Normal}(0.16, 0.25) \\
\sigma_\theta &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
\sigma_\beta &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
Rho &\sim \text{LJKCorr}(2) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, \beta, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)
\end{aligned}$$

Other models tested as part of this example mirrored these values.

23. Empirical Example Model and Priors

Here we start with the non-centered version of the multilevel multi-optima direct effect model with varying effects. Priors were set as discussed in the main text including $\bar{\theta}$ and $\bar{\beta}$ centered on the intercept and slope estimates from an ordinary least squares regression and scale parameter based on prior predictive simulation. Priors for parameters not discussed in the main text (i.e. those related to non-centered parameterization) were set based on prior predictive simulation and observing the posterior.

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(Y_{True,i}, Y_{SE,i}) \\
Y_{True,i} &\sim \text{MVNormal}(u_i, V) \\
u_i &= dmX_i \theta_{reg[i]} + X_{True,i} \beta_{reg[i]} \\
\theta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\theta} + v_{,1} \\
\beta_{reg[i]} &= \bar{\beta} + v_{,2} \\
v &= (\text{diag}(\sigma) LZ) \\
Z &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 1) \\
dmX_i &= f(t_{1/2}, T) \\
\bar{\theta} &\sim \text{Normal}(-1.18, 0.75) \\
\bar{\beta} &\sim \text{Normal}(6.30, 1.75) \\
\sigma &\sim \text{Exponential}(1) \\
L &\sim \text{LJKCorrCholesky}(4) \\
V &= g(t_{1/2}, v, T) \\
t_{1/2} &\sim \text{logNormal}(\log(0.25), 0.75) \\
v &\sim \text{Exponential}(20) \\
X_{Obs,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(X_{True,i}, X_{SE,i}) \\
X_{True,i} &\sim \text{Normal}(0, 1)
\end{aligned}$$

Other models tested as part of this example mirrored these values.

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Supplementary Figures for Grabowski, M (in press).
Blouch: Bayesian Linear Ornstein-Uhlenbeck models for
Comparative Hypotheses. Systematic Biology.

Mark Grabowski

April 4, 2024

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1 Phylogenies with selective regimes

Figure S1: Phylogeny for a) Simulation Example showing four color coded regimes; and b) Empirical Example for Cervidae dataset showing three regimes for breeding group size color coded following Figure 3.

2 Traceplots for simulation example

Figure S2: Traceplots for Simulation Example analysis for a) the multilevel multi-optima adaptive model with varying effects; and b) the non-multilevel version of the same model.

3 Results for Multilevel Multi-Optimum Adaptive Model with Varying Effects

Figure S3: Results for the Simulation Example using the multilevel multi-optima adaptive model with varying effects include color coded prior versus posterior plots for a) Phylogenetic half-life; b) Stationary variance (v); c) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA; and d) Posterior predicted means (solid black lines) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for intercepts and slopes. Species values for each regime are shown in colored circles matching Figure S1a, with priors for intercept and slope shown in light grey lines. Dotted lines are true values of intercept and slope parameters for each regime.

4 PSIS plots for simulation example

Figure S4: Pareto shape parameter k used to assess the reliability of the predictions for the Simulation Example using a) the multi-optima adaptive model with varying effects; b) the multilevel version of the same model. Values of $k < 0.7$ indicate the approximations are reliable.

5 Prior and Posterior Predictive Checks

Figure S5: Prior and posterior predictive checks for simulated samples for the best supported models for a,b) Simulation Example and c,d) Empirical Example. Density distribution in blue is original data, red is prior or posterior distribution.

6 Traceplots for empirical example

Figure S6: Traceplots for Empirical Example analysis for a) multi-optima direct effect model; b) multi-optima direct effect model with varying effects; c) the multilevel version of a; and d) and the multilevel version of b.

7 PSIS plots for empirical example

Figure S7: Pareto shape parameter k used to assess the reliability of the predictions for the Empirical Example using a) the multi-optima direct effect model with varying intercepts; b) the multi-optima direct effect model with varying effects; c) the multilevel version of a; and d) the multilevel version of b. Values of $k < 0.7$ indicate the approximations are reliable.

8 Results for Multi-Optimum Direct Effect Model with Varying Effects

Figure S8: Results for the Empirical Example using the multi-optima direct effects model with varying effects include color coded prior versus posterior plots for a) Phylogenetic half-life; b) Stationary variance (v); c) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA; and d) Posterior predicted means (colored lines matching Figure 3 and Figure S1b) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for intercepts and slopes. Species values for each regime are shown in colored circles matching Figure S1a, with priors for intercept and slope shown in light grey lines.

9 Results for Multilevel Multi-Optimum Direct Effect Model with Varying Effects

Figure S9: Results for the Empirical Example using the multilevel multi-optima direct effects model with varying effects include color coded prior versus posterior plots for a) Phylogenetic half-life; b) Stationary variance (v); c) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA; and d) Posterior predicted means (colored lines matching Figure 3 and Figure S1b) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for intercepts and slopes. Species values for each regime are shown in colored circles matching Figure S1a, with priors for intercept and slope shown in light grey lines.

10 Results for Multilevel Multi-Optimum Direct Effect Model with Varying Intercepts

Figure S10: Results for the Empirical Example using the multilevel multi-optima direct effects model with varying intercepts include color coded prior versus posterior plots for a) Phylogenetic half-life; b) Stationary variance (v); c) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA; and d) Posterior predicted means (colored lines matching Figure 3 and Figure S1b) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for intercepts and slopes. Species values for each regime are shown in colored circles matching Figure S1a, with priors for intercept and slope shown in light grey lines.

11 Results for Multi-Optimum Direct Effect Model

Figure S11: Results for the Empirical Example using the multi-optima direct effects model include color coded prior versus posterior plots for a) Phylogenetic half-life; b) Stationary variance (v); c) Covariance between residuals from the regression as a reflection of time since MRCA; and d) Posterior predicted means (colored lines matching Figure 3 and Figure S1b) and 89% compatibility intervals (light grey region) for intercepts and slopes. Species values for each regime are shown in colored circles matching Figure S1a, with priors for intercept and slope shown in light grey lines.

Supplementary Tables for Grabowski, M (in press). *Blouch*: Bayesian Linear Ornstein-Uhlenbeck models for Comparative Hypotheses. Systematic Biology.

Table S1. List of functions included in Blouch v 1.0. Columns include Stan function, OU model, *Blouch* Extension, Model Type, and R function to setup data for analysis.

Stan Function*	OU Model(s)	Extension	Model Type	Data Setup Function**
blouchOUdirect	Direct Effect			blouch.direct.prep
blouchOUadapt	Adaptation			blouch.adapt.prep
blouchOUdirect_adapt	Adaptation and Direct Effect			blouch.direct.adapt.prep
blouchOUreg	Multi-optima			blouch.reg.prep
blouchOUreg_mlm_vi	Multi-optima	Multilevel Model	Varying Intercepts	
blouchOUreg_direct	Multi-optima and Direct Effect Model			blouch.reg.direct.prep
blouchOUreg_direct_ve	Multi-optima and Direct Effect Model		Varying Effects	
blouchOUreg_direct_mlm_vi	Multi-optima and Direct Effect Model	Multilevel Model	Varying Intercepts	
blouchOUreg_direct_mlm_ve	Multi-optima and Direct Effect Model	Multilevel Model	Varying Effects	
blouchOUreg_adapt	Multi-optima and Adaptive Model			blouch.reg.adapt.prep
blouchOUreg_adapt_ve	Multi-optima and Adaptive Model		Varying Effects	
blouchOUreg_adapt_mlm_vi	Multi-optima and Adaptation Model	Multilevel Model	Varying Intercepts	
blouchOUreg_adapt_mlm_ve	Multi-optima and Adaptation Model	Multilevel Model	Varying Effects	
blouchOUreg_direct_adapt	Multi-optima, Direct Effect, and Adaptive Model			blouch.reg.direct.adapt.prep
blouchOUreg_direct_adapt_ve	Multi-optima, Direct Effect, and Adaptive Model		Varying Effects	
blouchOUreg_direct_adapt_mlm_vi	Multi-optima, Direct Effect, and Adaptation Model	Multilevel Model	Varying Intercepts	
blouchOUreg_direct_adapt_mlm_ve	Multi-optima, Direct Effect, and Adaptation Model	Multilevel Model	Varying Effects	

*Included multilevel models all have non-centered versions – not shown here – that have "_nc " after the function name. All models have both a prior predictive check and posterior predictive check version, with the Stan model endings “_priorpc” and “_postpc”, respectively. See online vignette for their usage.

**Each Stan function has an associated R function for formatting data appropriately. See online vignette for full examples.

Table S2. Marginal posterior distribution for Simulation Example using multi-optima adaptive model with varying effects including four regimes/optima and four different slopes (n=100). Results correspond to Figure 2.

Parameter	True value	Mean	sd	2.50%	25%	50%	75%	97.50%	<i>n_eff</i>	\hat{R}
$t_{1/2}$	0.10	0.08	0.03	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.1	0.16	1744	1
ν	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0	0.01	0.01	0.03	4826	1
θ_1	1.00	1.04	0.11	0.83	0.97	1.04	1.11	1.27	6266	1
θ_2	2.00	1.88	0.11	1.66	1.81	1.88	1.96	2.11	5995	1
θ_3	3.00	2.68	0.25	2.19	2.51	2.68	2.85	3.14	7129	1
θ_4	4.00	3.96	0.12	3.76	3.89	3.95	4.02	4.21	2926	1
β_1	0.75	0.73	0.07	0.6	0.69	0.73	0.78	0.86	6837	1
β_2	0.50	0.44	0.08	0.28	0.38	0.44	0.49	0.6	7370	1
β_3	0.35	0.15	0.17	-0.2	0.03	0.15	0.27	0.49	7508	1
β_4	0.25	0.28	0.05	0.17	0.24	0.28	0.31	0.39	7722	1

Results include true (known) value, mean, the standard deviation of the mean (SD), boundaries for the 2.5%, 25%, 50%,75% and 97.5% compatibility intervals (CI), the effective sample size statistic (*n_eff*) and the potential scale reduction statistic, \hat{R} . Estimated parameters include the phylogenetic half-life ($t_{1/2}$) [in units of tree height], the stationary variance (ν) [in units of squared *Y* trait units per unit tree height], the estimated optima/intercepts for regimes 1-4 (θ_{1-4}) [in units of *Y*], and the corresponding optimal slopes (β_{1-4}) [in units of *Y* per unit change in *X*].

Table S3. Marginal posterior distribution for Simulation Example using multilevel multi-optima adaptive model with varying effects including four regimes/optima and four different slopes (n=100). Results correspond to Figure S3.

Parameter	True value	Mean	SD	2.50%	25%	50%	75%	97.50%	n_{eff}	\hat{R}
$t_{1/2}$	0.10	0.08	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.17	903	1
v	0.01	0.01	0.01	0	0	0.01	0.01	0.02	5543	1
$\bar{\theta}$	-	2.55	0.54	1.49	2.17	2.54	2.89	3.66	6425	1
$\bar{\beta}$	-	0.34	0.16	-0.02	0.25	0.35	0.44	0.6	4402	1
ρ	-	-0.21	0.3	-0.74	-0.4	-0.23	0	0.39	7422	1
σ_1	-	1.25	0.39	0.69	0.98	1.18	1.47	2.21	5709	1
σ_2	-	0.37	0.22	0.12	0.22	0.31	0.45	0.95	3218	1
θ_1	1.00	1.02	0.11	0.82	0.95	1.02	1.09	1.25	4823	1
θ_2	2.00	1.87	0.11	1.66	1.8	1.87	1.94	2.1	7366	1
θ_3	3.00	2.74	0.28	2.15	2.57	2.75	2.93	3.24	4317	1
θ_4	4.00	3.96	0.13	3.75	3.88	3.95	4.02	4.25	1053	1
β_1	0.75	0.75	0.07	0.61	0.7	0.75	0.79	0.89	4271	1
β_2	0.50	0.46	0.08	0.3	0.4	0.46	0.51	0.62	6113	1
β_3	0.35	0.21	0.19	-0.21	0.09	0.22	0.34	0.54	4093	1
β_4	0.25	0.28	0.06	0.17	0.25	0.28	0.32	0.39	5066	1

Results include true (known) value, mean, the standard deviation of the mean (SD), boundaries for the 2.5%, 25%, 50%,75% and 97.5% compatibility intervals (CI), the effective sample size statistic (n_{eff}) and the potential scale reduction statistic, \hat{R} . Estimated parameters include the phylogenetic half-life ($t_{1/2}$) [in units of tree height], the stationary variance (v) [in units of squared Y trait units per unit tree height], the mean optima/intercept ($\bar{\theta}$)[in units of Y trait units] across regimes, the mean slope ($\bar{\beta}$)[in units of Y per unit change in X], the correlation between the mean optima/intercepts and slopes (ρ), the estimated standard deviation among the optima (σ_1) and slopes (σ_2)[in units of Y and of Y per unit change in X , respectively], the estimated optima/intercepts for regimes 1-4 (θ_{1-4}) [in units of Y], and the corresponding optimal slopes (β_{1-4})[in units of Y per unit change in X].

Table S4. Model comparisons using Pareto-Smoothed Importance Sampling for the Simulation Example. Results include model tested, expected log pointwise predictive density for a new dataset (elpd_loo), standard error of this statistic (elpd_loo (se)), difference between the model with the largest value of this statistic (elpd_diff), and standard error of the difference (se_diff). Results correspond to Figure S4

Model	elpd_loo	elpd_loo (se)	elpd_diff	se_diff
Multilevel multi-optima adaptive model with varying effects	30.2	6.4	0	0
Multi-optima adaptive model with varying effects	30.0	6.8	-0.2	0.6

All results calculated using the R package *loo* (Vehtari et al. 2023)

Table S5. Marginal posterior distribution for the Empirical Example using multilevel multi-optima direct effect model with varying effects for the relationship between posterior skull length and antler volume with breeding group size as a predictor. Results correspond to Figure S9.

Parameter	mean	SD	2.50%	25%	50%	75%	97.50%	n_{eff}	\hat{R}
$t_{1/2}$	0.24	0.06	0.14	0.2	0.23	0.27	0.38	5014	1
v	0.2	0.07	0.1	0.15	0.19	0.24	0.37	2217	1
$\bar{\theta}$	0.25	0.34	-0.55	0.08	0.28	0.46	0.87	1316	1
$\bar{\beta}$	5.55	0.82	4.01	5	5.5	6.04	7.29	1435	1
ρ	-0.06	0.34	-0.67	-0.31	-0.06	0.19	0.58	2942	1
σ_1	0.47	0.39	0.02	0.18	0.37	0.65	1.45	1525	1
σ_2	1.27	0.56	0.23	0.89	1.23	1.63	2.46	1573	1
θ_1	0.05	0.54	-1.21	-0.24	0.16	0.41	0.97	1176	1
θ_2	0.29	0.17	-0.05	0.18	0.29	0.4	0.62	4240	1
θ_3	0.48	0.22	0.05	0.33	0.48	0.62	0.92	3754	1
β_1	6.95	0.92	4.96	6.41	7.05	7.58	8.54	1197	1
β_2	4.54	0.59	3.41	4.15	4.53	4.92	5.72	3607	1
β_3	4.75	0.6	3.55	4.35	4.75	5.16	5.95	4041	1

Results include mean and 95% compatibility interval (CI), the standard deviation of the mean (SD), the effective sample size statistic (n_{eff}) and the potential scale reduction statistic, \hat{R} . Estimated parameters include the phylogenetic half-life ($t_{1/2}$) [in units of tree height], the stationary variance (v) [in units of squared trait units (log antler volume) per unit tree height], the mean optima/intercept ($\bar{\theta}$) [in units of log Antler Volume (l)] across regimes, the mean slope ($\bar{\beta}$) [in units of log Antler Volume (l) per change in log Posterior Skull Length (cm)] across regimes, the correlation between the mean optima/intercepts and slopes (ρ), the estimated standard deviation among the optima (σ_1) and slopes (σ_2) [in units of log Antler Volume (l) and of log Antler Volume (l) per change in log Posterior Skull Length (cm), respectively], the estimated optima/intercepts for increasing breeding group sizes (θ_{1-3}) [in units of log Antler Volume (l)], and the corresponding slopes (β_{1-3}) [in units of log Antler Volume (l) per change in log Posterior Skull Length (cm)].

Table S6. Marginal posterior distribution for the Empirical Example using the multilevel multi-optima direct effect model with varying intercepts for the relationship between posterior skull length and antler volume with breeding group size as a predictor. Results correspond to Figure S10.

Parameter	mean	se_mean	SD	2.50%	25%	50%	75%	97.50%	n_eff	\hat{R}
$t_{1/2}$	0.22	0	0.06	0.13	0.18	0.21	0.25	0.35	5542	1
v	0.24	0	0.08	0.12	0.19	0.23	0.29	0.43	2746	1
θ_1	-0.98	0.01	0.46	-1.87	-1.29	-1	-0.69	-0.02	2051	1
θ_2	0.22	0	0.2	-0.17	0.08	0.21	0.35	0.6	4251	1
θ_3	0.43	0	0.24	-0.05	0.27	0.44	0.59	0.9	3260	1
$\bar{\theta}$	-0.06	0.01	0.43	-0.94	-0.32	-0.06	0.21	0.83	2499	1
β	5.06	0.01	0.49	4.16	4.72	5.04	5.39	6.08	2359	1
σ	0.88	0.01	0.43	0.2	0.57	0.81	1.12	1.91	1729	1

Results include mean, the standard deviation of the mean (SD), boundaries for the 2.5%, 25%, 50%,75% and 97.5% compatibility intervals (CI), the effective sample size statistic (n_{eff}) and the potential scale reduction statistic, \hat{R} . Estimated parameters include the phylogenetic half-life ($t_{1/2}$) [in units of tree height], the stationary variance (v) [in units of squared trait units (log antler volume) per unit tree height], the mean optima/intercept ($\bar{\theta}$)[in units of log Antler Volume (l)] across regimes, the estimated optima/intercepts for increasing breeding group sizes (θ_{1-3}) [in units of log Antler Volume (l)], and the estimated slope (β) [in units of log Antler Volume (l) per change in log Posterior Skull Length (cm)], and the estimated standard deviation among the optima (σ) [in units of log Antler Volume (l)].

Table S7. Marginal posterior distribution for the Empirical Example using multi-optima direct effect model with varying intercepts for the relationship between posterior skull length and antler volume with breeding group size as a predictor. Results correspond to Figure S11.

Parameters	mean	SD	2.50%	25%	50%	75%	97.50%	n_eff	\hat{R}
$t_{1/2}$	0.11	0.06	0.04	0.07	0.09	0.13	0.26	1905	1
v	0.19	0.07	0.09	0.14	0.18	0.23	0.35	1401	1
θ_1	-1	0.29	-1.55	-1.19	-0.99	-0.81	-0.42	2666	1
θ_2	0.27	0.16	-0.05	0.17	0.26	0.37	0.58	3511	1
θ_3	0.49	0.17	0.14	0.38	0.49	0.6	0.82	2663	1
β	4.78	0.42	3.99	4.49	4.76	5.05	5.71	2560	1

Results include mean, the standard error of the mean (se_mean), the standard deviation of the mean (SD), boundaries for the 2.5%, 25%, 50%,75% and 97.5% compatibility intervals (CI), the effective sample size statistic (n_{eff}) and the potential scale reduction statistic, \hat{R} . Estimated parameters include the phylogenetic half-life ($t_{1/2}$) [in units of tree height], the stationary variance (v) [in units of squared trait units (log antler volume) per unit tree height], the estimated optima/intercepts for increasing breeding group sizes (θ_{1-3}) [in units of log Antler Volume (l)], and the estimated slope (β) [in units of log Antler Volume (l) per change in log Posterior Skull Length (cm)].

Table S8. Model comparisons for the Empirical Example using Pareto-Smoothed Importance Sampling. Results include model tested, expected log pointwise predictive density for a new dataset (`elpd_loo`), standard error of this statistic (`elpd_loo (se)`), difference between the model with the largest value of this statistic (`elpd_diff`), and standard error of the difference (`se_diff`). Results correspond to Figure S7.

Model	<code>elpd_loo</code>	<code>elpd_loo (se)</code>	<code>elpd_diff</code>	<code>se_diff</code>
Multi-optima direct effect model with varying effects	-26.2	4.3	0	0
Multilevel multi-optima direct effect model with varying effects	-25.3	4	-0.9	0.9
Multi-optima direct effect model (standard)	-27.4	4.8	-2.1	3
Multilevel multi-optima direct effect model with varying intercepts	-27.8	5.2	-2.6	3.3

All results calculated using the R package *loo* (Vehtari et al. 2023)

References

Vehtari A, Gabry J, Magnusson M, Yao Y, Bürkner P, Paananen T, Gelman A (2023). “loo: Efficient leave-one-out cross-validation and WAIC for Bayesian models.” R package version 2.6.0, <https://mc-stan.org/loo/>